

Gene regulatory network inference in the era of single-cell multi-omics

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Abstract | The interplay between chromatin, transcription factors and genes generates complex regulatory circuits that can be represented as gene regulatory networks (GRNs). The study of GRNs is useful to understand how cellular identity is established, maintained and disrupted in disease. GRNs can be inferred from experimental data — historically, bulk omics data — and/or from the literature. The advent of single-cell multi-omics technologies has led to the development of novel computational methods that leverage genomic, transcriptomic and chromatin accessibility information to infer GRNs at an unprecedented resolution. Here, we review the key principles of inferring GRNs that encompass transcription factor–gene interactions from transcriptomics and chromatin accessibility data. We focus on the comparison and classification of methods that use single-cell multimodal data. We highlight challenges in GRN inference, in particular with respect to benchmarking, and potential further developments using additional data modalities.

Introduction

Cells regulate gene transcription to coordinate cellular activities in response to intracellular and extracellular signals. Transcription is largely regulated by **transcription factors [G]** (TFs), proteins that bind to specific sequences of DNA (**DNA binding sites [G]**) and can have positive or negative effects on the transcriptional rate of target genes¹. Genomic DNA is tightly packed with structural proteins into complexes known as nucleosomes, which are the basic unit of **chromatin [G]**, making most genes inaccessible to the transcription machinery. To enable transcription, the region near a gene transcription start site, known as the **promoter [G]**, needs to be exposed by displacing tightly packed nucleosomes. Changes in DNA accessibility can be triggered by the binding of so-called pioneer TFs². Other TFs can bind to distal **cis-regulatory elements [G]** (CREs) of the DNA and, together with cofactors and other proteins, cooperatively enable the recruitment and

stabilization of the RNA polymerase protein complex that synthesizes mRNA from the gene body DNA (**Fig. 1a**).

Gene regulatory networks [G] (GRNs) are interpretable computational models of the regulation of gene expression in the form of networks, mathematically also defined as graphs. Multiple components of gene regulation, such as TFs, splicing factors, long noncoding RNAs, microRNAs and metabolites, can be incorporated in GRNs. Here, we focus on their simplest representation, which captures only the interplay between TFs and target genes, whereby the nodes of the GRN consist of genes, some of them being TFs, and the edges of the GRN represent regulatory interactions between the genes (**Fig. 1b**). Other possible GRN representations are discussed elsewhere³⁻⁶. Uncovering the topology and the dynamics of GRNs is fundamental to understanding how cellular identity is established and maintained⁷, which has important implications for engineering cell fate⁸ and for disease prevention⁹.

Understanding GRNs is a long-standing quest in biology, as illustrated by the seminal work from the 1960s characterizing the bacterial lactose (lac) operon¹⁰. Reconstructing large-scale GRNs became a major focus of systems biology, leveraging various high-throughput experimental methods and computational algorithms¹¹⁻¹³. Historically, GRNs have been commonly assembled from experimentally validated regulation events compiled in databases¹⁴⁻¹⁷ or inferred *de novo* from gene coexpression in bulk transcriptomics data¹⁸⁻²⁰. If sufficient transcriptomics data are available, GRNs can be inferred that are better contextualized for the biological question at hand than GRNs extracted from databases, which tend to be generalistic. However, transcriptomics data do not directly capture many underlying regulatory mechanisms, such as the TF protein abundance and DNA binding events, cooperation of TFs and cofactors, alternative transcript splicing, post-translational protein modification events, and the accessibility and structure of the genome. The inclusion and measurement of these other aspects of gene regulation has the potential to generate GRNs that better represent gene regulation in vivo (**Fig. 1b**). For example, the inclusion of chromatin accessibility²¹ data allows to fine-tune TF–gene links by considering whether genes are open and by including CREs in the inference of GRNs.

Furthermore, bulk profiling provides mixed measures across cell types in a tissue sample and thus cannot disentangle regulatory programmes specific to particular cell types or cell states^{22,23}. This limitation has been overcome by the use of single-cell technologies^{24,25}, allowing the inference of GRNs across different cell types, differentiation trajectories and conditions (**Fig. 1c**). For this reason, and with the introduction of multimodal profiling technologies²⁶⁻²⁸, there has been a recent explosion of novel GRN inference methods.

In this Review, we outline general principles of GRN inference and their potential limitations. Furthermore, we describe how multimodal readouts can be leveraged to infer more accurate GRNs, and we classify and briefly describe several novel tools that have been developed for this task. In addition, we highlight possible

downstream GRN analyses and how to assess experimentally the obtained results. Finally, we discuss current challenges and future directions in the field.

A

Figure 1 | **Principles of gene regulatory networks.** **a**, Schematic depiction of gene regulation and its key elements. Transcription factors (TFs) bind to promoter regions and cis-regulatory elements (CREs), displacing nucleosomes and making the transcription start site (TSS) accessible. Cooperation between TFs, cofactors and other proteins allows for the recruitment and stabilization of the RNA polymerase protein complex, which synthesizes mRNA from the gene body DNA. **b**, Gene regulatory networks (GRNs) can be inferred from measured omics data and, through the modeling of additional information such as TF binding predictions or chromatin accessibility, can be refined to better resemble the true underlying GRN. The nodes of the GRN are TFs and their regulated genes, and the edges between nodes indicate the mode of regulation (activation or inhibition). **c**, GRNs generated from single-cell omics data allow to: understand cell type and state specificity, explain the evolution of dynamic trajectories, and identify differences between conditions.

Inference of GRNs

GRN inference refers to the process of summarizing gene regulation — a highly complex and dynamic process — into an interpretable network structure from data using computational methods. It is based on the assumption that the effects of a true underlying GRN can be observed and measured in molecular data²⁹ (**Fig. 1b**). Interactions in GRNs can be directed or undirected (denoting a causality relationship between genes or lack of it, respectively), signed (denoting the mode of regulation, positive or negative) and/or weighted (denoting the strength of the interaction).

From transcriptomics data

Methods in this category fit models that try to explain the observed variability of gene expression based on the expression of other genes. Weighted Gene Co-expression Network Analysis (WGCNA)¹⁹ is one of the simplest and most popular approaches. It carries out pairwise correlations across the whole transcriptome to identify modules of co-expressed genes. The resulting network is commonly known as a gene co-expression network and its interactions are undirected owing to the symmetrical nature of correlations. Although this strategy is useful to identify gene modules in an unsupervised manner, the lack of causal regulatory links hinders its interpretability and typically yields a large number of false positive associations. To address these limitations, methods such as GENIE3²⁰ and its faster implementation GRNBoost2³⁰ first distinguish TFs from target genes based on previously reported regulatory activity³¹ and then train models that predict the expression of target genes based solely on the expression of TFs, which markedly reduces the number of interactions to be considered. By doing so, undirected interactions are turned into directed connections and thus introduce putative causal relationships. Nevertheless, inference from transcriptomics data alone

introduces false positives as many other mechanisms that are involved in gene regulation, such as chromatin accessibility, are ignored. Moreover, because many processes are required for a mRNA transcript encoding a TF to become a functional protein, transcript levels alone might not be informative enough^{1,32}. These limitations may hinder the inference process, as it has been shown that, overall, these methods tend to have moderate success in accurately inferring GRNs³³⁻³⁵.

From TF binding data or chromatin accessibility

Assays such as **chromatin immunoprecipitation followed by sequencing [G]** (ChIP-seq)³⁶ and **cleavage under targets and tagmentation [G]** (CUT&Tag)³⁷ enable TF binding to be measured across the genome. This information can be used to build GRNs directly by assigning TF binding sites to putative target genes³⁸. However, despite some high-throughput alternatives³⁹⁻⁴¹, profiling of TF binding is still costly and limited to TFs for which antibodies are available. In addition, the use of TF binding data alone typically requires the assignment of bound TFs to their target genes by closest genomic proximity, ignoring possible distal interaction events that are known to be relevant in gene regulation¹. By contrast, a pioneering study explored the integration of ChIP-seq data and transcriptomics data to enable a more refined assignment of TFs to genes⁴².

An alternative approach is to use chromatin accessibility data to infer gene regulatory elements that are potentially targeted by TFs. The most commonly used technology owing to its simple and relatively cheap protocol is the **assay for transposase accessible chromatin with sequencing [G]** (ATAC-seq)²¹, but other technologies exist such as DNase-seq⁴³ and NOME-seq⁴⁴ (reviewed elsewhere⁴⁵). Methods that leverage chromatin accessibility data split GRN inference into two steps: first, the assignment of TFs to gene regulatory elements (open chromatin regions, commonly referred to as **peaks [G]**); and second, the assignment of these regulatory elements to genes (**Fig. 2**). For the first step, methods leverage TF binding motif databases and **motif matcher algorithms [G]** to make binding predictions for TFs on accessible CREs (**Box 1**). For the second step, methods link accessible CREs to genes that are within a certain genomic distance. The distance cutoff is based on the observation that distal CREs such as **enhancers [G]** or **silencers [G]** generally interact with the promoter regions of genes at a typical distance¹. Some examples of such inference methods include ATAC2GRN⁴⁶, LISA⁴⁷ and SPIDER⁴⁸. These methods assume that if the promoter region of a gene is accessible, the gene is being transcribed, but that might not always be the case.

Figure 2 | **Flowchart of methods for gene regulatory network inference.** Methods for gene regulatory network (GRN) inference involve different steps depending on the data modalities generated for the samples or cells being studied. Transcriptomics data are first preprocessed and normalized to build a gene expression matrix, containing the transcript levels of each gene across samples or cells. A list of known transcription factor (TF) genes is obtained from other sources to distinguish genes with regulatory capabilities. Interactions between TFs and target genes are then inferred by building models that try to predict the observed gene expression from TF transcript abundance, generating TF–gene associations. Finally, the obtained interactions are aggregated and represented as a GRN. Chromatin accessibility data are first preprocessed and peaks are called to build a peak accessibility matrix, containing binary information about the openness of cis-regulatory elements (CREs) across samples or cells. CREs are associated to genes based on genomic distance limits, and TFs are predicted to bind to CREs using TF binding motif databases and motif matcher algorithms. Together, this information is used to obtain TF–CRE–gene triplets. Finally, these interactions are simplified into TF–gene pairs and aggregated into a GRN. When samples are profiled by both transcriptomics and chromatin accessibility (multi-omics data), preprocessing of each modality is carried out and, if needed, the unpaired modalities are integrated. Having both modalities available, methods can simultaneously leverage the three aforementioned modeling steps to build TF–CRE–gene triplets, which then are simplified and aggregated into a GRN.

Box 1 | Binding motif databases and motif matcher algorithms to assign transcription factors to open chromatin regions

Generating genome-wide binding data for multiple transcription factors (TFs) requires laborious experiments, so methods for gene regulatory network (GRN) inference instead predict TF binding events on open genomic regions based on prior information. This information comes from a large collection of TF–DNA binding assays, such as chromatin immunoprecipitation followed by sequencing (ChIP-seq) experiments³⁶, that can be used to extract the most likely genomic sequence to which a given TF specifically binds, commonly known as a TF binding motif²⁰⁸. Several databases have collected such assays and generated TF binding motif collections for model organisms. Because coverage between databases may vary, they can be merged to increase the number of TFs considered in the GRN inference process. Moreover, several computational algorithms have been developed that leverage TF binding motifs to predict binding events, known as motif matcher algorithms. All of these algorithms are based on computing the probability of a TF binding event from the motif sequence and filtering the significant ones. Because the different methods model TF binding differently, results may vary between them and should be considered during GRN inference. The Table lists the TF binding motif databases and motif matcher algorithms used across the reviewed methods.

Name	URL	Ref
Binding motif databases		
CIS-BP	http://cisbp.cabr.utoronto.ca/	209
cisTarget databases	https://resources.aertslab.org/cistarget/databases/	67
ENCODE	http://compbio.mit.edu/encode-motifs	210
HOCOMOCO	https://hocomoco11.autosome.org/	211
JASPAR	https://jaspar.genereg.net/	212
TRANSFAC	https://genexplain.com/transfac/	213
UniPROBE	http://thebrain.bwh.harvard.edu/uniprobe/	214
Motif matcher algorithms		
FIMO	http://meme.sdsc.edu/	215
GimmeMotifs	https://gimmemotifs.readthedocs.io/	216

HOMER	http://homer.ucsd.edu/homer/motif/	68
MOODs (as implemented in motifmatchr)	https://github.com/jhkorhonen/MOODS https://github.com/GreenleafLab/motifmatchr	217,218
motifanalysis (as implemented in reg-hint)	https://reg-gen.readthedocs.io/	219
PIQ toolkit	https://bitbucket.org/thashim/piq-single/src/master/	220
PWMScan	https://ccg.epfl.ch/pwmtools/pwmscan.php	221
pycisTarget	https://pycisTarget.readthedocs.io/	67

From single-cell data

GRN inference methods using bulk omics data have enabled the characterization of genome-wide regulatory events but, in the case of mixed samples such as tissues, they cannot capture cell type or state specificity of GRNs^{22,23}. In addition, GRN inference methods require large sample sizes to generate sufficient data, which can become prohibitively costly in bulk profiling.

With the emergence of single-cell technologies, particularly single-cell RNA sequencing (scRNA-seq), GRN reconstruction methods have been used to infer cell type-specific TF–gene interactions, together with the dynamic changes that occur in these GRNs across development and conditions (**Fig. 1c**)⁴⁹. One of the first GRN inference methods tailored to scRNA-seq data was SCENIC⁵⁰, an extension to the GRNBoost2³⁰ method, which generates cell type-specific GRNs by exploiting TF–gene co-expression patterns and, in addition, prunes the edges of the GRN based on TF binding motif enrichment on gene promoter regions. The improved resolution of single-cell measurements also enables the identification of dynamic cell states and their transitions that may not be easily differentiated into distinct groups, such as during development, cell differentiation or disease progression^{51,52}. Pseudotime ordering characterizes these continuous changes and can be used to inform GRN inference. The resulting GRNs provide valuable insights into the complex processes involved in key fate decisions. LEAP⁵³ and SINCERITIES⁵⁴ are examples of GRN inference methods that leverage pseudotime ordering to infer the directionality between genes in the GRNs. The use of contrast level statistics obtained after differential testing^{55,56} is an effective means of identifying differences between conditions, such as between healthy individuals and a disease patient cohort. This strategy differs from computing differences between GRNs, as explained in the later section describing ‘Downstream GRN analyses’.

Recent advances in single-cell chromatin accessibility profiling (such as scATAC-seq)⁵⁷, which can be carried out together with single-cell transcriptomics^{26–28}, have allowed for the refinement of GRN reconstruction at an unparalleled definition. Some early works inferred GRNs from unpaired multi-omics data to study human myeloid cell differentiation⁵⁸, mouse embryonic development⁵⁹ and HIV infection of dendritic cells⁶⁰. However, they did not provide their method implemented as a tool for others to use. These were followed by an explosion of novel methods for GRN inference that leverage both scRNA-seq and scATAC-seq (**Fig. 2; Table 1**) (**Supplementary Box 1**). The multimodal data used for GRN inference can be paired if both measurements come from the same cell or unpaired or if they come from different cells. Some methods do not require matching chromatin accessibility and gene expression profiles for each cell, as they either summarize readouts across groups of cells or build GRNs independently for each modality followed by a merging step. By contrast, other methods model both modalities in the same cell simultaneously. In these ‘simultaneous’ methods, unpaired data can still be modeled if both modalities are matched using integration approaches⁶¹. To facilitate usage, some of these methods (for example, DeepMAPS⁶², FigR⁶³, GLUE⁶⁴, scAI⁶⁵ and SOMatic⁶⁶) implement their own integration approach.

Table 1 | Existing tools for inference of gene regulatory networks from multi-omics data

Tool ^a	Possible inputs	Type of multimodal data	Type of modeling	Type of interactions	Statistical framework	Default motif database / motif matcher	Default upstream and downstream distance cutoffs	Language	Ref
ANANSE	Groups, contrasts	Unpaired	Linear	Weighted	Frequentist	CIS-BP / GimmeMotifs	100 kb / 100 kb	Python	84
CellOracle	Groups, trajectories	Unpaired	Linear	Signed, weighted	Frequentist or Bayesian	CIS-BP / GimmeMotifs	500 kb / 500 kb	Python	76
DC3	Groups	Unpaired	Linear	Binary	Frequentist	Undefined / HOMER	Based on Hi-C	Python	88
DeepMAPS	Groups	Paired or integrated	Linear	Weighted	Frequentist	JASPAR / PWMScan	150 kb / 150 kb or exon	Python	62
Dictys	Groups, trajectories	Unpaired / Paired or integrated	Linear	Signed, weighted	Frequentist	HOCOMOCO / HOMER	500 kb / 500 kb	Python	81
DIRECT-NET	Groups	Paired or integrated	Nonlinear	Binary	Frequentist	JASPAR / MOODs	250 kb / 250 kb	R	72
FigR	Groups	Paired or integrated	Linear	Signed, weighted	Frequentist	CIS-BP / MOODs	50 kb / 50 kb	R	63
GLUE	Groups	Paired or integrated	Nonlinear	Weighted	Frequentist	JASPAR / cisTarget	150 kb / 150kb	Python	64
GRaNI	Groups	Paired or integrated	Linear	Weighted	Frequentist	JASPAR, HOCOMOCO	250 kb / 250 kb	R	71

						/ PWMscan			
Inferelator 2.5	Groups	Unpaired	Linear	Signed, weighted	Frequentist or Bayesian	CIS-BP, ENCODE, TRANSFAC / FIMO	10 kb / 10 kb	Python	203
Inferelator 3.0	Groups	Unpaired	Linear or nonlinear	Weighted	Frequentist or Bayesian	JASPAR / FIMO	50 kb / 2.5 kb	Python	77
IReNA	Trajectories	Unpaired	Linear	Signed, weighted	Frequentist	TRANSFAC / FIMO	250 kb / 250 kb	R	80
MAGIC AL	Groups, contrasts	Unpaired	Nonlinear	Weighted	Bayesian	CIS-BP, ENCODE / MOODs	Based on Hi-C	R / MATLAB	166
MICA	Groups	Unpaired	Nonlinear	Signed, weighted	Frequentist	HOCOMOCO, JASPAR / motifanalysis	Nearest transcription start site	R	204
Pando	Groups	Paired or integrated	Linear or nonlinear	Signed, weighted	Frequentist or Bayesian	JASPAR, CIS-BP / MOODs	100 kb / Gene body	R	78
PECA	Groups	Paired or integrated	Linear	Weighted	Bayesian	JASPAR, TRANSFAC, UniPROBE / HOMER	1,000 kb / 1,000 kb	MATLAB	73
Regulatory Motifs	Groups	Paired or integrated	Linear	Signed	Frequentist	HOCOMOCO / motifanalysis	5 kb / 5 kb	MATLAB	205
RENIN	Groups	Paired or integrated	Linear	Signed, weighted	Frequentist	CIS-BP / MOODs	500 kb / 500 kb	R	206
scAI	Groups	Paired or integrated	Linear	Weighted	Frequentist	CIS-BP / MOODs	250 kb / 250 kb	R	65
sc-compReg	Groups, contrasts	Unpaired	Linear	Binary	Frequentist	Undefined / undefined	Undefined	R	85
SCENIC+	Groups, contrasts, trajectories	Paired or integrated	Linear	Signed, weighted	Frequentist	CisTargets / cisTarget	150 kb / 150 kb	Python	67
scMEGA	Trajectories	Paired or integrated	Linear	Weighted	Frequentist	JASPAR / MOODs	250 kb / 250 kb	R	79
scMTNI	Groups, trajectories	Unpaired	Linear and nonlinear	Weighted	Bayesian	CIS-BP / PIQ	5 kb / 5 kb	C++	82
SOMatic	Groups	Unpaired	Linear	Binary	Frequentist	HOCOMOCO / FIMO	50kb / 50kb	C++	66
Symphony	Groups	Unpaired	Linear	Signed, weighted	Bayesian	Undefined / FIMO	Nearest transcription start site	Python	74,75
TimeReg	Groups, trajectories	Paired or integrated	Linear	Binary	Frequentist	Undefined / HOMER	Undefined	MATLAB	83

TRIPOD	Groups	Paired or integrated	Nonlinear	Signed, weighted	Frequentist and Bayesian	HOCOMOCO, JASPAR / MOODs	100 kb / 100 kb	R	²⁰⁷
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^aFurther detail regarding these tools and their methodologies is provided in Supplementary Box 1.

Multimodal GRN inference methods use an extended framework to that used by single-modality methods to reconstruct GRNs. Specifically, they predict gene expression from TF gene expression, they assign TFs to accessible CREs using binding motif information, and they associate CREs with target genes constrained by genomic distance (**Fig. 2**). For the prediction of TF binding events, different methods use different, highly heterogeneous TF binding motif databases and prediction algorithms (**Box 1; Table 1**). As TF binding motif databases have different coverage of TFs, and prediction algorithms model binding differently, results between GRN inference methods might differ even if they use similar modeling strategies. The majority of methods allow for using different TF binding motif databases than their default, but most methods fix the motif matcher algorithm used — except for SCENIC+⁶⁷, which implements three algorithms, cisTarget⁶⁷, DEM⁶⁷ and HOMER⁶⁸. In addition, GRN inference methods use different genomic distance cutoffs to assign open chromatin regions to target genes. Some consider close distances up to 10 kb, others medium distances up to 100 kb, others large distal effects up to 1,000 kb, and others do not specify the distance cutoff either in the original publication or in the source code (**Table 1**). Given that functionally validated interactions are greatly enriched at the closest distances, and that they substantially fall-off by 100 kb^{1,69}, differences in distance cutoffs will likely affect the resulting inferred GRN.

After carrying out the above steps (**Fig. 2**), multimodal GRN inference methods generate a candidate scaffold network made up of triplets of a TF associated with a CRE that is linked to a target gene. To generate a final GRN structure, different mathematical strategies are used. Some of these strategies assume a linear relationship between TFs, CREs and genes, and others assume a nonlinear relationship (**Table 1**). Linear modeling assumes that one variable, for example gene transcripts, changes in direct proportion to another variable, for example TF transcripts or CRE openness. By contrast, nonlinear modeling can accommodate more complex interactions between variables such as synergistic effects⁷⁰. Although it is widely acknowledged that gene expression is a nonlinear process⁷⁰, linear modeling of GRNs is often preferred owing to its simplicity in formulation and interpretation. Independently of the modeling strategy used, the significance of the obtained regulatory interactions can be assessed using either frequentist or Bayesian probability statistical frameworks (**Table 1**). A frequentist approach defines the probability of an event as the proportion of times that the event occurs in a large number of identical experiments, whereas Bayesian probability defines it as a measure of confidence in the occurrence of said event based on both observed data and previous information. Bayesian methods can take into account available prior knowledge but they usually require larger computational resources than frequentist approaches, which can be a limitation when inferring

genome-wide GRNs with large-scale single-cell data. In addition, the success of Bayesian inference depends on the quality of the prior knowledge used. Therefore, when no prior information is available or it is suspected to be inaccurate, frequentist inference might be more accurate.

Multimodal GRN inference methods can be grouped based on the combination of their modeling strategy and the types of input they accept (**Table 1**). The majority of methods are designed to model GRNs across distinct groups, usually cell types, by frequentist regression. FigR⁶³ and GRaNIE⁷¹, among others, use frequentist linear regression; DIRECT-NET⁷² and SCENIC+⁶⁷ use frequentist nonlinear regression (random forest); and PECA⁷³ and Symphony^{74,75} use Bayesian modeling. By contrast, CellOracle⁷⁶, Inferelator 3.0⁷⁷ and Pando⁷⁸ offer multiple modeling strategies to the user. In case no distinct groups can be defined from the data owing to its continuous nature, for example in cell development, scMEGA⁷⁹ and IReNA⁸⁰ leverage trajectories to infer GRNs linearly and nonlinearly, respectively. Also, Dictys⁸¹, scMTNI⁸² and TimeReg⁸³ use a combination of both cell type grouping and trajectory data to inform the GRN modeling, whereas CellOracle⁷⁶ and SCENIC+⁶⁷ use the latter to carry out downstream analyses. ANANSE⁸⁴, sc-compReg⁸⁵ and SCENIC+⁶⁷ build group-specific (for example, cell type-specific) GRNs but can also leverage gene contrast statistics during the inference process.

Downstream GRN analyses

Once GRNs have been inferred from any resolution and combination of omics data, they can be queried using various downstream analyses to provide novel biological insights (**Box 2; Fig. 3**).

Box 2 | Successful applications of gene regulatory networks derived from single-cell multi-omics data

Gene regulatory networks (GRNs) have been used in various contexts to answer a range of research questions; here, we summarize some recent examples.

- A multimodal time course of human brain organoids was generated using single-cell RNA-sequencing (scRNA-seq) and single-cell assay for transposase accessible chromatin with sequencing (scATAC-seq)⁷⁸. Using the GRN inference tool Pando, the authors predicted transcription factor (TF) binding sites and inferred a global GRN underlying organoid development. By making *in silico* predictions from the GRN followed by a CRISPR-based screen, they identified GLI3 as an essential TF for cortical fate establishment.
- A multimodal atlas of the fly brain was generated using scRNA-seq and scATAC-seq, and characterized developmental, reprogramming and maturation trajectories²²². Using a deep learning model trained on the omics data, the authors inferred cell type-specific TF binding predictions and used this to decode the regulatory grammar of enhancer architectures that underlie neuronal diversity.

- CellOracle was introduced as a mathematical model to carry out in silico TF perturbations from GRNs trained using single-cell multi-omics data⁷⁶. In the context of zebrafish development, the authors made systematic predictions of TF knockouts, which allowed the identification of new roles for key regulators of early zebrafish development, including *noto* and *lhx1a*.
- A multimodal atlas of mouse early organogenesis was built by profiling gene expression and chromatin accessibility from individual cells⁸⁷. The authors developed in silico ChIP-seq, a method to predict TF binding sites, and used it to characterize the GRNs underlying the transition of neuromesodermal progenitors to somitic mesoderm. Using the CellOracle⁷⁶ framework for in silico predictions, followed by experimental validation, they characterized a role of Brachyury in priming cis-regulatory elements for differentiation.
- scRNA-seq and scATAC-seq were carried out on cortical tissue from patients with Alzheimer's disease⁹⁰. By modelling relationships between TFs, cis-regulatory elements and target genes, the authors identified ZEB1 and MAFB as candidates involved in gene regulation and, potentially, disease progression in neurons and microglia.
- Inferelator 3.077 was used to infer GRNs for several CD4+ memory T cell populations from mice and benchmarked their results by curating TF knockout and ChIP-seq data for 42 of the identified TFs²²³. Then, they integrated the obtained GRNs with cell-cell communication networks, and functionally validated a regulatory circuit involving Il-6, Maf and Cd153 in T follicular helper cells important for antibody-mediated vaccine responses in aged mice.

Figure 3 | **Applications of gene regulatory networks.** **a**, Topological analysis. Network centrality measures can be used to identify hubs of transcription factors (TFs) or genes within a gene regulatory network (GRN) that are highly connected. Clustering of nodes based on their connectivity gives rise to sub-network modules that can be associated with biological functions. **b**, Comparative analysis. Comparison of the connectivities in different GRNs by the pairwise subtraction of TF–gene interactions between GRNs can provide insight into the rewiring of gene regulation between different cell types, individuals, conditions or organisms. **c**, Inference

of TF activity. GRNs can be coupled to enrichment methods to infer which TFs might be functionally active from transcriptomics data. GRNs inferred from multi-omics data can be then used to infer TF activities in other contexts, such as independent single-cell, spatial or bulk transcriptomics data. **d**, *In silico* perturbation experiments. GRNs can be used to simulate perturbation experiments by propagating changes in gene expression through the network over short iterations. Then, the obtained simulated gene expression profiles can be used to infer cell fate decisions.

Topological analysis

Although GRNs are simple and interpretable models of gene regulation, they can still contain large numbers of genes and an even larger number of interactions between them. **Network centrality [G]** measures can help to identify which TFs or genes are more important for the connectivity or the information flow of the network (**Fig. 3a**). Some examples of network centrality measures include **degree centrality [G]**, **closeness centrality [G]**, **betweenness centrality [G]** and **eigenvector centrality [G]**. These measures have been useful to identify TFs that drive cell fate changes in diverse biological contexts, such as direct lineage reprogramming⁷⁶, human myocardial infarction⁸⁶ and mouse development⁸⁷.

Another approach to characterize the topology of GRNs are methods based on spectral graph theory, which explore the properties of a network when represented as a matrix. For example, non-negative matrix factorization applied to the adjacency matrices of GRNs has identified groups of TFs that cooperatively drive lineage transitions in mouse embryonic stem cells^{83,88}. Similarly, clustering of GRN topology identified known regulators in human haematopoietic cell differentiation⁷⁰ and in the response of macrophages to interferon- γ ⁷¹. The gene regulatory modules that are obtained can then be enriched for gene sets to characterize their potential biological functions⁸⁹.

Comparative analysis

The comparative analysis of GRNs can uncover the rewiring events that drive differences between cell types, cell states, disease states, treatment approaches and organisms (**Fig. 3b**). The easiest method for comparative analysis involves the pairwise subtraction of TF–gene interactions between GRNs. This methodology has identified key regulators in subpopulations of B cells in patients with lymphocytic leukaemia⁸⁵, groups of TFs for trans-differentiation of fibroblasts to different human cell types⁸⁴, candidate Alzheimer’s disease-specific trans-regulators⁹⁰ and cell state-specific regulators in human T cells^{74,75}. It has also been used to assess evolutionary conservation of TF–gene interactions and adaptation of transcriptional regulation across species⁹¹. However, owing to the sparse and noisy nature of GRNs, direct comparison of TF–gene interactions

is often not sufficiently robust. Topic modeling strategies such as latent Dirichlet allocation⁹², an unsupervised Bayesian model that was originally developed for natural language processing, allow for generating dense, low-dimensional representations that filter noise in the structure of the GRN, and thus capture more robustly the differences in regulatory relationships. This strategy has been useful for predicting the survival of patients with cancer⁹³ and for identifying rewiring events in human haematopoiesis⁸².

Inference of TF activities

GRNs can be coupled with enrichment methods to infer TF activities from transcriptomics data^{15,50,94,95}. This approach allows for the observed gene expression to be integrated with the GRN topology to extract which TFs might have relevant roles in certain contexts (**Fig. 3c**). Common enrichment methods include GSEA⁹⁶, AUCCell⁵⁰ and VIPER⁹⁴, among others⁹⁵. In bulk studies, inference of TF activities through enrichment methods has enabled, for example, the identification of druggable oncoproteins⁹⁴, stratification of cell lines in response to drug treatment⁹⁷ and identification of a master regulator as a metastasis promoter in breast carcinoma⁹⁸. In single-cell studies, enrichment methods have identified a novel mechanism of immunotherapy resistance in human T cells⁹⁹, regulators and inducers of oligodendroglioma⁵⁰, and potential druggable targets for pathological fibroblasts in patients with COVID-19¹⁰⁰. These methods have also been recently applied to spatially resolved transcriptomics data, for example to suggest regulators involved in the functional transition of cardiomyocytes across the border zone that surrounds ischemic lesions in human myocardial infarction⁸⁶.

Perturbation and prediction of cell fate

GRNs can be used to simulate gene expression values over time by propagating TF expression to target genes in an iterative manner. With this framework, *in silico* perturbations can be carried out by changing the expression of a candidate TF and then observing how it affects the resulting transcriptome after a given number of iterations (**Fig. 3d**). Afterwards, the simulated values can be compared with the gene expression of local neighbouring cells to estimate cell identity transition probabilities analogous to RNA velocity analysis¹⁰¹. First introduced by CellOracle⁷⁶, this strategy suggested the role of *Zfp57* in generating and maintaining mouse induced endoderm progenitors, which was later experimentally validated with *in vitro* perturbation experiments. SCENIC⁶⁷ used a similar strategy to identify *RUNX3* as a potential driver of melanocytes to mesenchymal melanoma cells, showcasing the ability of GRNs to capture and model complex regulatory events.

Experimental assessment of GRNs

The connections predicted by GRN inference methods should be seen as hypothetical regulatory interactions that must be assessed by complementary information and/or experiments. In this section, we discuss common practices for this purpose (Fig. 4).

Figure 4 | **Experimental assessment of gene regulatory networks.** Although there is no clear ‘ground truth’ for gene regulation, several experiments and analyses can be carried out to validate specific aspects of gene regulatory networks (GRNs). Interactions between transcription factors (TFs) can be queried in protein–protein databases for TFs that share large numbers of target genes and are assumed to interact. The presence of TF protein can be confirmed by proteomic assays, and the activation state of TFs can be assessed in targeted phosphorylation experiments. Links between TFs and cis-regulatory elements (CREs) can be confirmed by binding assays, such as chromatin immunoprecipitation followed by sequencing (ChIP-seq) and CAP-SELEX. Candidate CREs can be tested for regulatory capability with reporter assays or perturbation experiments. Alternatively, functional CREs can be assumed to be evolutionarily conserved or to be enriched in disease-associated GWAS loci. Links between CREs genes can be evaluated experimentally by genome conformation assays such as Hi-C or super-resolution microscopy, or by CRISPR-based perturbation experiments. Alternatively, databases of expression quantitative trait loci (eQTLs) may be used.

TF abundance and post-translational modification

The number of transcripts encoding a given TF is a limited proxy of its protein abundance, let alone its activity¹⁰². To this end, proteomics technologies can be used to measure the abundance of TFs. Targeted proteomics at single-cell resolution is still challenging but some technologies such as mass

spectrometry-based approaches or assays that use antibody–oligonucleotide conjugates are already available¹⁰³, reviewed elsewhere¹⁰⁴. Alternatively, databases such as The Human Protein Atlas^{105,106} can be queried to confirm if a candidate TF has been previously reported to be present at the protein level in a given tissue or cell type. In addition, post-translational modifications such as phosphorylation, ubiquitylation and methylation can affect TF localization, stability, activity and interaction with other proteins¹⁰⁷. The most highly studied post-translational modification of TFs is phosphorylation, which can be informative as to whether a TF is in an inactive or active form¹⁰⁸.

TF binding and cooperativity

GRN inference methods rely on TF binding predictions based on binding motif analysis to assign TFs to open chromatin regions in the genome. It is known that this type of prediction produces many false positives as a large number of TF binding motifs have low specificity¹⁰⁹. To this end, ChIP-seq³⁶, which as mentioned above measures the binding of TFs to DNA, can be used to test how many TF binding events were correctly predicted by the GRN inference method⁷⁶. Databases such as ChIP-Atlas¹¹⁰, EpiMap¹¹¹ and UniBind¹¹² compile large collections of ChIP-seq experimental data and organize them by organism, tissue and cell type, making them valuable resources for analysing GRN predictions. Because not all ChIP-seq peaks represent direct binding events of a TF, both EpiMap¹¹¹ and UniBind¹¹² implement (different) strategies to curate the data, thus providing more reliable information regarding TF binding sites. Another alternative is single-molecule footprinting, a technique that jointly measures TF binding and nucleosome occupancy at single DNA molecule resolution^{113,114}. It allows for checking the state frequency of each genomic region: bound by a TF, unbound but with open chromatin, or unbound and occupied by nucleosomes. The advantage of single-molecule footprinting over ChIP-seq is that it provides a dynamic and quantifiable state of TF binding instead of a binary description. GRN inference methods predict that several TFs bind to the same open genomic region, which is in keeping with the knowledge that TFs bind cooperatively to DNA to induce transcription^{1,115,116}. Another approach to assess the obtained GRN is to check whether the network has recovered the cooperative binding of TFs. Technologies such as CAP-SELEX¹¹⁷ enable cooperative interactions between selected TF pairs to be jointly profiled in the presence of DNA. Single-molecule footprinting can also be used for this purpose by checking the overlap of footprints. Other approaches include using protein–protein interaction assays¹¹⁸ or checking databases of previously annotated interactions¹¹⁹.

Regulatory activity of CREs

CREs can be in three different chromatin states: transcriptionally active, poised or repressive. Many of the reported open chromatin regions might not have a role in gene regulation, thereby increasing the number of false positives in GRN predictions. Therefore, experiments must assess whether candidate enhancers affect gene expression. Massively parallel reporter assay¹²⁰ is a technique that allows to test if candidate genomic regions can induce gene expression in episomal vectors. Another strategy is to carry out pooled CRISPR-based perturbations of candidate CREs followed by RNA sequencing to identify which regions of the genome affect gene expression^{69,121}. In addition, the Encyclopedia of DNA Elements (ENCODE) Consortium has catalogued, using various biochemical assays, more than one million candidate CREs with enhancer-like signatures that span ~16% of the human genome^{36,122,123}. As functional enhancers are evolutionarily conserved^{124,125}, another approach is to check for genomic sequence similarity across different species. When studying diseases, CREs in open chromatin regions can be scanned for **single nucleotide polymorphisms [G]** (SNPs) that have been previously linked to diseases in **genome-wide association studies [G]**. If candidate CREs are enriched for disease-associated SNPs, this suggests that those CREs are likely to be functional^{90,126}.

Linkage to target genes

Even if an open chromatin region is validated to have regulatory properties, it is necessary to test which specific genes it affects. Chromosome conformation capture techniques such as **Hi-C [G]**¹²⁷⁻¹²⁹ allow to measure the probability of contact between genomic regions and to identify **topologically associating domains [G]**. Because gene regulation is based on sustained genomic interactions^{130,131}, if a genomic region is consistently in close contact with the promoter region of a gene, it may regulate it. To this end, super-resolution microscopy has also been used to validate candidate CRE–gene interactions¹³², although with less throughput than Hi-C. Perturbation assays like CRISPR-based screens coupled with whole-transcriptome analysis allow for deleting or activating specific CREs and observing how this changes gene expression^{69,133}. In addition, databases of **expression quantitative trait loci [G]** in human populations can be used to validate distal candidate CREs¹³⁴⁻¹³⁶.

TF perturbation

A more direct approach to test whether a TF regulates a particular gene is to perturb TF expression and see how this affects gene expression. Technologies for pooled CRISPR (in)activation screens coupled with

whole-transcriptome readout are already available^{137–141}. The changes in gene expression upon TF perturbation can be used as ground truth to check how many of the affected genes are identified as target genes in the GRN^{135,95,142}. Also, one can see if the estimated TF activities (see previous section on ‘Inference of TF activities’) correspond to the perturbation that has been carried out (low or high TF activity for knockout or overexpression of the TF, respectively).

Challenges and future directions

The accumulation of omics datasets, particularly single-cell multi-omics data, in recent years has enabled a new wave of improved GRN inference strategies. An improved understanding of GRNs should pave the way to use these models not only as means to understand the principles of gene regulation, but also as tools to drive cell fate decisions for cellular engineering, enabling the generation of new cell types with new functions and the reprogramming of diseased cells to a healthy phenotype. The prospects are hugely promising, but many challenges remain regarding the modeling of GRNs and their use as predictive tools.

Integrating transcription and accessibility

The use of multi-omics data in principle allows for a better representation of gene regulation but also comes with its own challenges. As highly interrelated processes, chromatin accessibility and transcription are temporally coordinated. Yet, they have profoundly different kinetics and may be temporally shifted. These relationships are often not fully understood and it is typically assumed that paired chromatin accessibility and transcriptomics data in the same cell at a single time point are representative of the interplay between both processes^{143,144}. This limitation is compounded in the case of unpaired data if inadequate integration results in mismatched scATAC-seq and scRNA-seq data that will mislead the downstream modeling of GRNs¹⁴⁵. Novel integration strategies, such as that introduced by FigR⁶³, hold the promise to obtain better matching between cells. Among other factors, the temporal shift between chromatin accessibility and gene expression, as well as cooperative effects, gives rise to nonlinear relationships. Some of the GRN inference methods that we have discussed use nonlinear formulations to account for this, but they lose interpretability compared with linear models, and they often do not explicitly capture the sign of the interaction. For this reason, and for computational scalability, many methods still prefer to model gene regulation linearly. To improve the interpretability, SCENIC⁺⁶⁷ and IReNA⁸⁰ first infer regulatory interactions nonlinearly using random forests, and then they determine the sign of the interaction based on correlation analysis between TF and gene transcripts.

Scale and sparsity of single-cell data

GRN inference methods require a large number of observations that capture the variability of the biological process being studied. These observations can be individual cells, samples or conditions. Single-cell technologies generate thousands of profiles for a given sample, making it easier to infer GRNs in a larger variety of biological contexts than for bulk profiling technologies. Nonetheless, cells from the same sample are not necessarily independent and cannot be considered true biological replicates¹⁴⁶. For this reason, the inclusion of different samples might be needed to obtain meaningful GRNs. In addition, current single-cell GRN inference methods build an aggregate network across a population of cells and do not take into account that cells may come from different samples. A candidate approach to address this issue is LIONESS¹⁴⁷, which models the contribution of each sample when inferring GRNs and can generate sample-specific regulatory interactions. In addition, single-cell data are by nature sparse and noisy, particularly for data obtained by scATAC-seq, and proper filters need to be used to ensure a minimum quality^{148,149}. For paired multi-omics technologies, a systematic benchmark comparing their varying coverage and sensitivity to their single-omic counterparts is missing¹⁵⁰. Although sparsity is a known property of single-cell technologies^{151,152}, none of the GRN inference methods discussed here explicitly accounts for sparsity in its modeling. Some methods apply data transformations to counteract this limitation. Imputation methods can be used to reduce the number of ‘dropouts’ (caused by under-sampling of mRNAs or accessible DNA reads)^{153–155}, although it has been shown that they might have detrimental effects on GRN reconstruction¹⁵⁶. Strategies that aggregate similar cells into pseudobulk profiles or **metacells** [G]^{146,157,158} have been reported to be beneficial⁸⁷. Owing to its sparsity, most computational pipelines treat scATAC-seq data as binary data, assigning regions of the genome that are either accessible or closed for each cell. However, the true state of DNA accessibility is known to be more refined and can involve regions of intermediate accessibility that fluctuate in a dynamic manner¹⁵⁹. Thus, treating chromatin accessibility data as binary might be detrimental for downstream analyses^{160,161}, and methods that handle accessibility in a quantitative manner might improve GRN reconstruction^{154,155,162,163}.

The regulatory role of 3D genome structure

Current methods of GRN inference use arbitrary cutoffs based on genomic distance to assign CREs to genes. The aim of this filtering is to reduce the search space for each gene, requiring less computational resources, and to reduce the number of false positive interactions based on the fact that most genomic interactions are proximal⁶⁹. However, there are some examples of interactions between CREs and genes separated by large distances, such as enhancers of the *MYC* gene located almost 2Mb downstream of it¹⁶⁴. Depending on the distance cutoff that is used, GRN inference methods might miss crucial CRE–gene interactions. In addition, some interactions occur across chromosomes, as reported during olfactory receptor selection¹⁶⁵, which current

GRN methods are not able to consider. One solution to this problem is to use technologies based on 3D proximity, such as Hi-C^{127,129}, to assess whether a CRE might be regulating a gene. This strategy has been successfully applied by DC3⁸⁸ and MAGICAL¹⁶⁶. Despite some high-throughput alternatives^{167,168}, chromosome conformation capture techniques pose new challenges owing to their sparse nature¹⁶⁹, the fact that they still require integration with other modalities and their protocol can be hard to reproduce^{170,171}. Until they become more widely available, computational approaches have been used to predict the 3D structure of the genome based on accessibility data such as scATAC-seq data^{172,173}. Their use in GRN modeling has the potential to overcome the limitations of using distance-based cutoffs.

Refinement of TF binding predictions

The current strategy used by GRN inference methods of assigning TFs to CREs relies on TF binding motif databases (**Box 1**). Each database has a different coverage of motif collections, which might bias the resulting predictions. Motif databases are based on data from previous binding experiments such as ChIP-seq. However, it is estimated that there are no available binding data for 10% of the approximately 1,600 sequence-specific TFs encoded in the human genome^{31,109}. TFs without known binding motifs are excluded from GRN modeling, a factor that is exacerbated for non-model organisms as they tend to have fewer known TF binding motifs than other more well-studied organisms. One possible solution to incorporate missing TFs might be to leverage known protein–protein interactions during GRN inference. Moreover, current TF binding motifs are based on data from multiple tissues and cell types. It is known that TF binding is a highly context-specific process¹, and although the available motifs are still relevant for many tissues, cell type-specific motif models might help to increase the accuracy of TF binding predictions. Recent computational strategies based on deep-learning allow for cell type-specific TF binding predictions^{174,175}. These models are trained to predict cell type-specific DNA accessibility solely based on DNA sequence. Once trained, they identify which nucleotides are predicted to affect accessibility the most through in silico mutagenesis or by using strategies of interpretable machine learning such as SHAP¹⁷⁶. To derive cell type-specific TF binding predictions, these methods combine the predicted nucleotide quantifications with binding motifs. Although these strategies have the potential to better contextualize GRN inference, they require pretrained models using large amounts of data and are still limited to known TF binding motifs. With the accumulation of high-quality cell atlases from consortium initiatives^{49,177,178}, we envision that these strategies could eventually replace classic TF binding motif predictions. Furthermore, current TF binding predictions are binary but a quantitative definition could be more informative. BANC-seq¹⁷⁹, a technology that measures quantitative TF binding affinities, has the potential to generate more accurate GRNs.

Emerging multi-omics for GRN inference

The paired profiling of transcriptomics and chromatin accessibility data has enabled the potentially more accurate inference of GRNs but it is still a costly assay, limiting its widespread use. Newer alternatives such as ISSAAC-seq¹⁸⁰ enable multi-omics profiling at a much lower cost than the commercial 10x Multiome kit. Despite this, it might be the case that joint scRNA-seq and scATAC-seq data alone do not provide enough information to characterize gene regulation fully. In that case, advances in single-cell multi-omics profiling technologies that include more data modalities will be crucial¹⁸¹. Among such promising technologies is NEAT-seq¹⁸², which simultaneously profiles intra-nuclear proteins, chromatin accessibility and gene expression, allowing to discard possible false positives in GRN modeling by including TF protein abundance. Another example is scChARM-seq¹⁸³, which simultaneously profiles DNA methylation, chromatin accessibility and gene expression. Their joint profiling allows for TF assignment to CREs to be fine-tuned according to their methylation status. Moreover, ATAC-STARR-seq¹⁸⁴ can carry out massively parallel reporter assay and chromatin accessibility profiling simultaneously to test the transcribing capacity of open CREs. Advances in untargeted single-cell proteomics and phosphoproteomics may enable the profiling of functionally active TFs¹⁸⁵. One example is Phospho-seq¹⁸⁶, a novel technology that profiles chromatin accessibility and phosphorylated proteins at the single-cell level. Genetic information is known to be heterogeneous among populations of individuals but most methods assume that they share the same genome¹⁸⁷. scGET-seq¹⁸⁸, a technology that jointly profiles the genome and chromatin accessibility, has the potential to aid the inference of causal GRNs by testing how SNPs may affect chromatin accessibility owing to changes in TF binding affinities.

Benchmarking of GRNs

The benchmarking of GRNs is crucial to understand the accuracy of novel GRN inference methods, in particular those that leverage multi-omics data, which have not yet been evaluated systematically. Unfortunately, the validation of predicted GRNs is a complicated task as there is no clear ‘ground truth’ for gene regulation. One approach to benchmarking is to build *in silico* GRNs that allow us to assess GRN reconstruction against a known ground truth³⁴, yet one that might not well reflect true biological GRNs. As mentioned in the previous section, there are different methodologies that can be used to assess indirectly the quality of the predicted gene regulation events but these have certain limitations. Even if TF binding to a gene is observed, it does not necessarily mean that the TF regulates that gene as TFs bind stochastically into open regions of DNA and require cooperation with other molecules for effective regulation of transcription¹⁵⁹. Chromosome conformation capture technologies provide contact information and define topologically associating domains. However, their resolution might not be sufficient to detect certain genomic

interactions¹⁸⁹. High-resolution Hi-C maps exist such as Micro-C¹⁹⁰ but their cost becomes prohibitive when comparing many experimental conditions. To address this, machine learning approaches are being used to impute higher-coverage Hi-C maps from lower-coverage data to increase their resolution¹⁹¹. Another possibility is to use super-resolution microscopy-based alternatives, but their throughput is rather limited¹⁸⁹. TFs cooperatively drive gene expression but they do so mainly as a result of DNA-mediated interactions rather than protein–protein contacts¹¹⁷. Therefore, the evaluation of TF–TF interactions might be limited to particular cases only. The evaluation of GRNs through the use of perturbation experiments is a more promising approach owing to its inherent causality. However, perturbation screens are costly, sometimes do not work as expected and may be hindered by compensatory mechanisms and unaccounted for downstream effects. In addition to all of these limitations, as gene regulation is a time-dependent process, it might be the case that experiments contradict themselves because they captured a different time frame or because of experimental noise. Because the generation of a true ‘gold standard’ of gene regulation seems out of reach for the moment, we are more inclined to use these different assessment strategies as a collection of ‘silver standards’. We envision that a computational tool that collects and distributes such information will be useful for the community to carry out quality control on the inferred GRNs and to benchmark novel GRN inference methods. Platforms such as the Open Problems for Single-Cell Analysis project¹⁹² offer a suitable infrastructure to run and evaluate the large variety of GRN inference methods. These would also enable the evaluation of GRN inference methods in an unbiased manner through open competition, as was illustrated for GRN inference from bulk transcriptomics data by the DREAM challenges³³.

GRNs in the bigger picture

It is important to keep in mind that GRNs are not isolated. The classic example of the lac operon, whereby a metabolite (lactose) triggers gene regulation, highlights that GRNs are part of an entangled cellular machinery, including signaling and metabolic processes. The addition of single-cell phosphoproteomics and metabolomics¹⁹³ opens the possibility of linking gene regulation to cell signaling processes using context-specific network models¹⁹⁴.

Furthermore, cells rarely work as autonomous systems, and gene regulation is highly coordinated within tissues. Thus, another promising direction will be the integration of multimodal data with spatial information. In particular, we envision the integration of GRNs with intracellular and intercellular communication processes^{195–197} into spatially aware models^{198,199}. These strategies can help in understanding multicellular regulatory processes in time and space²⁰⁰.

Conclusions

Advances in high-throughput, single-cell multimodal technologies together with computational methods are paving the way to increasingly accurate GRN inference models. The large scale of the datasets makes it increasingly possible to train deep learning methods to predict gene expression from sequencing data^{175,201,202}. GRNs complement these approaches by giving a more interpretable model. Together, these different approaches might help to better understand differences in gene regulation across cell types, organs, populations and species, and serve as tools to control cell fate decisions. In the biomedical field, such knowledge could enable the identification of novel drug targets that control pathophysiological processes in different diseases.

Glossary

Transcription factors

(TFs). Proteins that modify the rate of transcription by binding to specific DNA sequences.

DNA binding sites

DNA sequences where transcription factors can bind to drive gene regulation, usually represented as nucleotide patterns known as motifs.

Chromatin

Higher-order filamentous structure of DNA–protein complex that can exist in a condensed or uncondensed state.

Promoter

Regulatory region in the genome located before the transcriptional start site of a gene.

Cis-regulatory elements

(CREs). Non-coding DNA regions that regulate transcription of nearby genes upon binding of transcription factors. These include promoters, enhancers and silencers.

Gene regulatory networks

(GRNs). Network representations of molecular interactions between transcriptional regulators and target genes.

Chromatin immunoprecipitation followed by sequencing

(ChIP-seq). Technique to analyze protein interactions with accessible DNA regions using chromatin immunoprecipitation followed by DNA sequencing.

Cleavage under targets and tagmentation

(CUT&Tag). Antibody-based technique to analyze protein interactions with accessible DNA regions using transposase Tn5-mediated tagmentation followed by DNA sequencing.

Assay for transposase-accessible chromatin with sequencing

(ATAC-seq). Technique to identify accessible DNA regions using hyperactive Tn5 transposase.

Peaks

Regions of accessible chromatin that form the readout of epigenetic sequencing techniques.

Motif matcher algorithms

String matching algorithms to detect transcription factor binding sites in DNA sequences.

Enhancers

Distal regulatory DNA regions where transcription regulatory proteins can bind and activate transcription.

Silencers

Distal regulatory DNA regions where transcription regulatory proteins can bind and repress transcription.

Network centrality

A group of graph theory metrics that defines the relative importance of a node in a network.

Degree centrality

Network centrality measure describing the number of edges (degree) of a node.

Closeness centrality

Network centrality measure describing the average distance (length of the shortest path) of a node to all other nodes.

Betweenness centrality

Network centrality measure representing the number of appearances of a node in the shortest path of any other two nodes in the network.

Eigenvector centrality

Network centrality measure describing the importance of a node in the network based on the centrality of its neighbours.

Single nucleotide polymorphisms

(SNPs). DNA sequence variations caused by substitution of a single nucleotide in a specific position.

Genome-wide association studies

Analysis approach to identify frequently appearing single nucleotide polymorphisms in the genome across a large cohort of individuals.

Hi-C

Technique to study chromatin conformation in three dimensions to identify genomic sequences that might be distal to each other in linear distance but closer in the 3D space.

Topologically associating domains

Self-interacting genomic regions with high interaction frequency of sequences within the domain and relative isolation from neighbouring regions, forming a three dimensional chromosome structure.

Expression quantitative trait loci

Genomic locations whose sequence variation is associated with changes in gene expression.

Metacells

Groups of cells with a similar molecular profile that can be aggregated into a single omics profile to reduce sparsity of the data.

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Author contributions

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Supplementary materials

Supplementary Box 1 | Detailed description of multimodal GRN inference tools

ANANSE¹

ANANSE infers cell type specific GRNs from unpaired RNA-seq and ATAC-seq data provided as a collection of open peaks BAM files, and normalized gene expression text files, one file for each sample and modality. It assigns TFs to open peaks by predicting the probability of DNA binding using a logistic

regression model previously trained on a large collection of ChIP-seq data from REMAP². To predict TF binding probabilities, this model leverages both the observed binary peak accessibility and the motif scores obtained from running the motif matcher algorithm GimmeMotifs³ with the motif database CIS-BP⁴. To assign peaks to genes, ANANSE weights interactions by their genomic distance, by default up to 100 kb from the gene TSS. The greater the distance of a peak to the TSS, the lower is its weight. Based on this, it computes a TF-gene binding score by aggregating all the binding probabilities across peaks weighted by genomic distance. It fits a linear regression model with ridge regularization having the observed binary peak accessibility as response variable and the previously obtained motif scores as coefficients to generate TF activity scores, these being the fitted motif coefficients. To model the final GRN, ANANSE computes an interaction score by mean-scaling the ranks of the four scores: (1) TF gene expression, (2) target gene expression, (3) TF binding score and (4) TF activity. The final TF-gene interactions range from 0, suggesting no regulation, to 1, likely to be regulated. Additionally, ANANSE can construct a differential GRN from a source and target network from different cell types or conditions. Combining the differential GRN with the results of differential expression testing results, it computes an influence score that can be used to rank TFs by relevance in the contrast.

CellOracle⁵

CellOracle uses scRNA-seq data to infer context-specific GRNs from a base GRN built from ATAC-seq data in an unpaired manner. Typically, the base GRN is created from a cell type- or sample-specific scATAC-seq matrix stored in a Cell Data Set object. First, promoter and proximal enhancer regions are identified by locating the TSS of a gene within the accessible ATAC-seq peaks using the annotations from HOMER⁶. Distal regulatory elements are then identified based on co-accessibility of regions using CICERO⁷. Peaks are considered as distal regulatory elements if they have a co-accessibility score of at least 0.8 with a peak containing a TSS, and are within 500kb from it. Next, TFs are associated with peaks through TF motif scanning by GimmeMotifs³ python package and its motif database, with a false positive rate threshold. Each identified TF-gene link is then included in the base GRN. For the contextualization of the GRN, raw transcript counts stored in an AnnData object are used to divide the dataset into several clusters based on gene expression to identify specific cell types or cell states. For each cluster, a linear regression model is used to predict the expression of a target gene based on the expression of the potential regulatory genes. Hereby, CellOracle estimates edge strengths for each TF-gene interaction using Bayesian Ridge regression, or Bagging (bootstrap aggregating) Ridge regression. The resulting distribution of edge strength coefficients is used to calculate a p-value for the edge strength by performing a one-sample *t*-test to determine whether the coefficient is significantly different from zero. Finally, TF-gene interactions can be selected based on the p-value and the absolute mean of the edge strength coefficient to form the final contextualized GRN.

DC3⁸

DC3 leverages non-negative matrix factorization to simultaneously deconvolute bulk or single-cell RNA-seq, ATAC-seq and Hi-C data and integrate these unpaired modalities. It constructs cell type specific GRNs with a linear modeling approach from pre-computed expression matrices, openness matrices and loop counts provided as text files. DC3 identifies key regulators for each cell type by first generating pseudo-bulk RNA and ATAC profiles. From the ATAC profiles it matches TFs to peaks using HOMER⁶ with an undefined motif database, and computes a motif enrichment score that depends on the motif enrichment's p-value and the fold change of the TF's expression. TFs are then selected for each cell type based on their gene expression level, their motif enrichment score and if they are significantly differentially expressed compared to at least one of the other cell types. Instead of a genomic distance-based approach, DC3 assigns peak-gene pairs based on loop counts from Hi-C data. Next, the model generates TF-peak-gene triplets by computing the correlation between the TF and target gene expression. Then, TF-gene interaction weights are assigned as the sum, over possible triplets, of the product of the motif score and the loop count. Finally, nodes of the GRN are classified into one of three categories: (1) Core, when a node acts both as a regulator and as a target, (2) upstream, when a node acts only as a regulator, and (3) downstream, when a node acts only as a target.

DeepMAPS⁹

DeepMAPS is a deep-learning framework that projects paired single-cell multiomics data into a heterogeneous graph representation finding the joint embedding of both cells and genes. It then infers a GRN for each recovered cell-type cluster. Therefore, the user has to provide gene expression and chromatin accessibility count matrices in H5-format, ATAC-fragment TSV-files and TF binding information from the JASPAR database¹⁰. The peak-gene links are inferred by computing a regulatory potential score for each peak located within 150 kb up- or downstream of the TSS or within the exon region of a gene, as implemented in MAESTRO¹¹. The regulatory potential score is defined as the product of the openness and the regulatory potential weight of a peak, with the weight describing the genomic distance of the peak to the TSS (+/- 150 kb or in the exon region). TF-peak links are identified by computing a binding affinity score using PWMScan24 with TF binding motifs from JASPAR¹⁰, passing a certain p-value threshold. Next, a regulatory intensity score is calculated for each TF-gene link in a given cell as the product of the sum of the regulatory potential scores and the sum of all binding affinity scores of all relevant peak-gene and TF-peak links, respectively. A regulon activity score is computed for each TF across cells in a given cluster based on the regulatory intensity scores of its target genes. Regulons are tested for differential activity between clusters with the Wilcoxon rank-sum test. Regulons with a p-value smaller than 0.05 and a logFC greater than 0.10 are considered cluster-specific. The final GRN is constructed by merging all cluster-specific regulons. Lastly, the TF nodes are ranked based on their Eigenvector centrality and the top 10 highest ranking TFs are identified as cluster-specific master TFs.

Dictys¹²

Dictys infers steady-state GRNs from groups such as cell types or dynamic GRNs along a trajectory from unpaired scRNA-seq data and bulk or scATAC-seq data provided as an RNA read count matrix stored in a TSV file and ATAC reads as a BAM file. Dictys first constructs a scaffold network from ATAC-seq data. Therefore, pseudo-bulk chromatin accessibility peaks are called with MACS2¹³ and the top 500,000 peaks are kept. Later, the Wellington bootstrap procedure from pyDNase¹⁴ is used to annotate TF footprints, and HOMER⁶ to scan the peaks for TF motifs from either HOMER⁶ or HOCOMOCO¹⁵. TF-gene links are estimated as the maximum value of the sum of the probability of the footprint annotation, the purity of the motif, and the distance to the gene in a maximum window of 500 kb from the TSS. The top 20 TFs for each gene are kept in the initial scaffold network. In the next step this network is refined by modeling the kinetics of gene expression as a function of the transcriptional regulation strength of each possible TF that links to that gene while also modeling technical variation. The modeling of gene expression kinetics is based on an Ornstein-Uhlenbeck stochastic process where the steady-state distribution represents the biological expression variation for each cell. Technical variation is modeled by sparse binomial sampling. Their modeling procedure results in kinetic gene regulatory networks that account for feedback loops and can simulate gene perturbations from which the final regulatory network with direct and indirect relations is derived. Dictys further allows dynamic GRN inference from trajectories provided by the user where moving windows are defined to first generate static individual GRNs followed by gaussian kernel smoothing and the creation of a combined dynamic network.

DIRECT-NET¹⁶

DIRECT-NET builds cell type specific GRNs from paired scRNA-seq and scATAC-seq multiome data or scATAC-seq alone. The data is provided as 10x h5 feature count matrices along with a fragment TSV file from which a Seurat object is created. First, DIRECT-NET creates pseudo-cells by aggregating the gene expression and/or chromatin accessibility profiles of similar cells selected based on a KNN graph in a user-defined low-dimensional representation of the data. The obtained aggregated profiles for both omics are normalized by scaling factors as implemented in DESeq2¹⁷. To identify functional peak-gene links, DIRECT-NET builds a nonlinear regression model based on XGBoost¹⁸. For each gene, it starts by identifying its promoter peak 500 bp upstream and enhancer peaks 250 kb upstream and downstream from the TSS. When only ATAC-seq data is available, the model predicts the observed aggregated promoter

accessibility based on the aggregated accessibility of other potentially linked peaks. When both omics are available, the model predicts the observed aggregated gene expression based on the aggregated accessibility of other potentially linked peaks. For each distal peak, the model returns an importance score corresponding to how important that peak is for predicting the expression of a given gene. Next, DIRECT-NET detects high-confidence functional peaks by overlapping all peaks with an importance score higher than the median overall importance scores with the differentially accessible peaks in each cell type. Then, TFs are assigned to peaks using the motif scanning method MOODs¹⁹ and the JASPAR¹⁰ motif database. Finally, the GRN is constructed by only keeping links to genes that are considered as marker genes of the given cell type.

FigR²⁰

FigR generates GRNs from paired RNA-seq and ATAC-seq data. It first generates peak-gene-links by computing the Spearman correlation of the peak accessibility and the gene expression of all peaks within a search window of 50 kb up- and downstream of the TSS of a given gene. Next, significant peak-gene links were identified by testing against permuted correlation coefficients from random background peaks with a one-tailed *z*-test. Only significant peak-gene pairs with a positive correlation were kept. FigR then identifies gene sets called domains of regulatory chromatin (DORCs) with a high-density of peak-gene interactions. For each set and cell an accessibility score is calculated by summing the mean-centered normalized counts of the significantly associated peaks. To infer links from TFs to these regulatory sets FigR calculates a regulation score. Therefore, it combines the Spearman correlation between TF expression and the accessibility score of the regulatory region set with the relative enrichment of TF motifs from the CIS-BP⁴ database in the same set as identified by the motif matching algorithm MOODs¹⁹. For each DORC, it identifies the *k* nearest neighbor DORCs based on the smoothed DORC scores matrix and selects the union of itself and their associated peaks, creating a pool of peaks. Using the TF-peak associations, it calculates TF frequencies for the pooled peaks and for a permuted set of background peaks (*n* = 50) selected by chromVAR²¹, allowing it to test for significance using a *z*-test. The regulation score for each TF-DORC pair depends on the direction of the correlation and the significance of both the enrichment and correlation. In the final GRN, positive values mean that a given TF positively regulates a downstream DORC and negative values the opposite.

GLUE²²

GLUE simultaneously learns feature and cell embeddings from different single-cell modalities stored as AnnData objects. The former are learnt by training a graph autoencoder on a prior biological knowledge graph linking peaks in promoter regions to the corresponding genes. A feature embedding space is then defined. The latter are learnt by training one variational autoencoder per modality, which also uses the feature embeddings to map back the cell embeddings to their input space. After training, when applied to scATAC-seq and scRNA-seq data, GLUE can infer peak-gene links based on the cosine similarity between feature embeddings (FDR corrected *p*-value inferior to 0.05). Peak-gene connections can then be filtered on different criteria, e.g. distance to TSS (window of 150 kb considered in their study case) or information from Hi-C and eQTL data. The pySCENIC framework will then be adapted to take advantage of these cis-regulatory links. First, the genome is scanned to establish TF-peak links based on TF binding motifs. Both GLUE-inferred peak-gene connections and motif-supported TF-peak binding links are integrated into TF-gene cis-regulatory hypothesis, which are ponderated by the number of ATAC peaks in common for each TF-gene couple. Second, GRNBoost2 is applied to the scRNA-seq data, measuring TF-gene associations based on coexpression. Finally, the expression-based network is pruned with the cis-regulatory rankings to preserve TF-gene connections with cis-regulatory evidence. To not miss regulations only because no ATAC peak is measured near a gene body, a second set of TF-gene regulatory links is defined. The pipeline is similar, but the GLUE inferred peak-gene links are simply replaced by association between genes and TSS flanking regions. The two sets of regulatory interaction are kept separated in the final output.

GRaNIE²³

GRaNIE infers cell type specific GRNs from paired bulk or single-cell chromatin accessibility peak and RNA-seq count tables. For single-cell data the transcriptome and ATAC-seq profiles are stored in a multimodal Seurat object. Raw data is subjected to DESeq2's¹⁷ median of ratios or quantile normalization and filtered for low read counts and long peak widths. Next, predicted TFBS from all TFs, either self pre-computed or compiled from PWMscan²⁴ with the HOCOMOCO¹⁵ or JASPAR¹⁰ databases, are overlapped with the open chromatin peaks. GRaNIE then computes pairwise Pearson correlations across samples between the TF's expression levels and each peak signal. For each TF, the correlations are discretized into bins, for each of which an empirical FDR is computed by dividing the number of TF-peak links without an identified TFBS by the total number of TF-peak links in that bin. Additionally, TFs can be classified as putative activators or repressors based on the distribution of correlations for peaks with and without a TFBS. Similar to the inference of TF-peak links, GRaNIE identifies peak-gene links based on the Pearson correlation of the gene expression level and the peak signal of each peak within 250 kb from the TSS. Optionally, Hi-C data can be used to infer the spatial chromatin structure and replace the genomic distance-based approach by testing only peak-gene pairs with a topologically associated domain. For peak-gene links an FDR is calculated by performing multiple testing adjustment using Benjamini-Hochberg. By default, the final GRN consists of the combination of TF-peak links from bins passing an FDR of 0.2 and peak-gene links with a positive correlation and an FDR smaller than 0.1. GRaNIE also provides a number of quality controls, including the assessment of positive versus negative peak-gene correlations to judge the signal to noise ratio and the employment of a permutation-based approach for comparison.

Inferelator 2.5²⁵

Inferelator 2.5 constructs steady state GRNs using unpaired bulk RNA-seq and bulk ATAC-seq data. It first generates a prior scaffold GRN from ATAC-seq data and motif information provided as a BED file of accessible peaks, a directory of TF motif PFMs and a BED file of genomic feature locations (TSS, gene body). Peaks are assigned to genes when they are within a search window of 10 kb up- and downstream of the gene body. Next, it leverages motif information from CIS-BP⁴, ENCODE²⁶ and TRANSFAC²⁷ databases and scans linked peak regions with FIMO²⁸ to find significantly enriched TF motifs. Inferelator 2.5 models gene expression as a multivariate linear combination of TF activities and TF-gene interactions. It first estimates TF activities by fitting a model in which the explained variable is the observed gene expression, and the covariates are the binary topology of the scaffold GRN and the unknown TF activities. TF activity estimates are obtained by finding the least-squares solution. To obtain the TF-gene interaction coefficients, it builds a sparse regularized linear model of gene expression based on the previously obtained TF activities while incorporating prior information as evidence of TF-gene links in the scaffold GRN via a non-negative penalty matrix. In the final GRN, high-confidence TF-gene links are prioritized based on the partial correlation between TF and gene.

Inferelator 3.0²⁹

Inferelator 3.0 constructs GRNs from unpaired bulk or single-cell RNA-seq and ATAC-seq data employing a multi-task learning method. The expression data is clustered and submitted as separate learning tasks from which individual GRNs are inferred. It first generates prior scaffold GRNs from ATAC-seq data and motif information provided as BED files of peaks, a MEME file of TF motifs along with a reference GTF and FASTA file. Peaks are assigned to genes when they are within a window of 50 kb upstream and 2.5 kb downstream of the TSS. Next, it leverages motifs from JASPAR¹⁰, CIS-BP⁴ and TRANSFAC²⁷ and scans peaks with FIMO²⁸ to find significant TFs. For each TF-peak link, an effective information content (EIC) score is computed based on the probability of observing a specific base in each position of the motif sequence. The TF-gene binding score is then defined as the maximum EIC value. For each TF, these binding scores are clustered and only TF-gene pairs in the cluster with the highest scores are kept, generating a sparse prior network. Next, TF activities are estimated by fitting a multivariate linear model with gene expression as the explained variable, the binarized prior GRN and the TF activities as covariates. For each gene, Inferelator

3.0 then builds bootstrapped regularized multivariate linear models that predict gene expression as a weighted sum of estimated TF activities. Finally, for each gene, the model is refitted but leaving a given TF out to compute the amount of variance explained for that interaction. Edges are ranked by the variance explained, rank-combined across bootstraps into a single GRN and rank-based confidence scores are assigned. This is done for each cluster present in the data (e.g. cell types or time series). Finally, the cluster-wise GRNs are aggregated generating a unified GRN.

IReNA³⁰

IReNA builds a GRN for a given trajectory from unpaired scRNA-seq and bulk or scATAC-seq data. To run IReNA, the user has to provide fragment BAM files, peak-gene-link text files and footprint BED files along with a Seurat object of the gene expression data with pseudotime information stored in the metadata. First, IReNA identifies a GRN per modality and then intersects them. For the integrated omics, it identifies a user-defined trajectory using Monocle2³¹, smoothes the expression and epigenomic profiles across the trajectory and performs differential expression and accessibility analysis. For the scRNA-seq GRN, IReNA selects genes that are significantly differentially expressed and TFs that are expressed in >5% of the cells, TFs being genes that are included in the motif database TRANSFAC²⁷. From these it infers TF-gene pairs based on co-expression in the transcriptomics data, by running the random forest regression algorithm GENIE3³². To determine the sign of the interaction, it computes the Pearson correlation between the paired genes' expression levels. For the ATAC-seq GRN, IReNA first identifies differentially accessible peaks. Next, it infers peak-gene links by correlating the peak accessibility with the expression of each gene in a +/- 250 kb search window around the TSS as implemented in ArchR³³. TF binding events in differentially accessible peaks are detected using HINT³⁴. High-quality binding locations are then scanned for motifs by FIMO²⁸ with the motif database TRANSFAC²⁷. Finally, it generates an integrated GRN by intersecting both RNA-seq and ATAC-seq GRNs. Further downstream, IReNA can modularize the inferred GRNs by grouping differentially expressed gene and TFs into modules using *k*-means clustering on the smoothed expression profiles. The ideal number of modules is estimated by computing the silhouette scores. Modularized GRNs can then be analyzed for enriched TFs and simplified by pruning the edges within modules by a significance cutoff.

MAGICAL³⁵

MAGICAL infers GRNs from unpaired scRNA-seq and scATAC-seq data. It requires a collection of input TXT-files storing information about the cell type annotations, candidate differentially expressed genes and differentially accessible peaks, the read count information from both modalities, prior information on TF binding motifs and topologically associated domains (TADs) obtained from Hi-C data. Candidate regulatory circuits are built by mapping TF motifs from the chromVAR²¹ motif library (including CIS-BP⁴ and ENCODE²⁶) to candidate peaks using the MOODs¹⁹ method. Peaks with at least one motif match are then linked to candidate genes if they are located within the same TAD. If no prior information on TADs is provided the user can specify a genomic distance to link peaks to genes. Integration of both data modalities is coupled to TF activity estimation and is based on the assumption that the distribution of TF activities in a given cell type are the same in cells from both modalities as long as they were obtained from the same sample. For each TF MAGICAL learns the distribution and then infers its activity in each cell. Finally, for each regulatory TF-peak-gene circuit in each cell type, the TF-peak binding and peak-gene looping confidence is inferred. MAGICAL is fitting a model in a Bayesian framework for each data modality respectively. First, the chromatin accessibility data is explained by TF-peak binding and the estimated TF activity and next, the gene expression data is explained by the peak-gene interaction and the regulatory region activity, being a combination of the two previously inferred variables. To obtain the final GRN high-confidence circuits are selected based on the computed posterior probability representing the sampling frequency in an iterative Gibbs sampling process. The output GRN is provided as an TXT file including the TF-peak binding confidence and peak-gene-interaction as edge weights.

MICA³⁶

MICA constructs a GRN based on mutual information (MI) of single-cell transcriptomic data which is then refined with information from unpaired chromatin accessibility data. MICA first generates a scaffold GRN from normalized scRNA-seq data stored in a SingleCellExperiment object. It builds a co-expression network, by calculating the similarity between two genes' expression levels using MI, which in contrast to correlation doesn't assume linearity, continuity, or other specific properties of the dependence. MICA then estimates P-values for each potential TF-gene link based on the empirical distributions of the calculated MI values. Next, MICA uses context-specific ATACseq data, provided as open peak BAM files, to refine the predicted TF-gene interactions. It identifies enriched TF motifs in the open regions with HINT³⁴ using motif information from JASPAR¹⁰ and HOCOMOCO¹⁵. Each TF assigned to an open region is then linked to the gene with the nearest TSS. TF-gene links identified in the co-expression network are then intersected with the TF-gene pairs derived from the chromatin accessibility leading to the final GRN.

Pando³⁷

Pando infers a gene regulatory network from paired scATAC-seq and scRNA-seq data stored in a Seurat object. It first selects candidate enhancer regions by intersecting ATAC consensus peaks with known conserved regions from PhasCons or pre-annotated conserved CREs from ENCODE²⁶. Next, all candidate regions are scanned for TF binding motifs using motifmatchr²¹. Binding motifs are collected from JASPAR¹⁰ and CIS-BP⁴ or inferred on the basis of protein sequence similarity to other TFs from the same family. Each regulatory region containing a TF binding motif is linked to a gene if it is either encompassing the gene body or 100 kb upstream of the TSS. Then, a generalized linear model is used that predicts gene expression based on accessibility probability of the peak that overlaps the binding region and TF gene expression. Thereby, it estimates an edge weight that can be interpreted as the regulatory effect of TF-binding site pairs on the downstream gene. These fitted coefficients are tested for significance using ANOVA/*t*-tests and corrected for multiple testing using Benjamini-Hochberg. TF-gene links are then filtered for significance and classified as negatively or positively regulating interactions based on the estimated coefficients. The resulting GRN can be further contextualized by incorporating specific accessibility profiles such as for lineage or physiological region by pruning regulatory links with a significantly lower chromatin accessibility. Additionally, Pando allows the integration of Hi-C data to determine peak-gene links based on TADs.

PECA³⁸

PECA is a probabilistic linear model that infers sample-specific GRNs from paired bulk RNA-seq and ATAC-seq data of different cell types or tissues. It models the distribution of the expression of genes based on the accessibility of peaks and the expression of TFs and chromatin regulators, so called cofactors. For that, it uses FPKM or TPM-normalized gene counts stored in a TXT file and chromatin accessibility data stored in BAM files as inputs. For each enhancer obtained from ENCODE²⁶, PECA identifies potential target genes located within 1,000 kb from the TSS. It then calculates a conditional fold change of openness and expression based on the correlation between the peak's accessibility and the genes' promoter region (2 kb upstream of the TSS) accessibility and the peak's accessibility and the expression of the potential target gene, respectively. Next, TFs are assigned to each peak using HOMER⁶ with the motif databases JASPAR¹⁰, TRANSFAC²⁷, and UniPROBE³⁹. Finally, PECA builds a model consisting of three components. (1) The cofactor binding is modeled by logistic regression based on the expression of TFs which are known binding partners of a cofactor according to the database BIOGRID⁴⁰. (2) The peak activity model predicts if a peak is active based on its accessibility value and the expression of cofactors predicted to bind in it also using logistic regression. (3) The gene expression model predicts gene expression as a Gaussian variable based on the linear combination of the expression of TFs and their TF-complexes that bind to predicted active peaks. Once the model is fitted, PECA extracts sample specific GRNs linking expressed TFs to downstream genes that are connected by an active peak.

Regulatory Motifs⁴¹

Zenere et al., 2021 introduce an unnamed method to infer GRNs from paired ATAC-seq and RNA-seq data based on regulatory motif identification. As input the method uses log-2 transformed RNA- and ATAC-seq count matrices and starts with building a scaffold GRN, by linking peaks to target genes if the TSS of a gene is within 3 kb up- or downstream of a given peak. Additionally, genes, whose TSS is situated within 5 kb up- or downstream of the TSS of the aforementioned gene, are also being associated with that peak. TFs are assigned to a peak by identifying peak footprints using HINT³⁴ which are matched to TF motifs from the HOCOMOCO¹⁵ database using the method motifanalysis⁴². From the scaffold GRN, the method identifies TF-peak-gene and peak-TF-gene regulatory motif triplets, and tests their expression/accessibility for conditional independence using partial correlation, keeping only significant ones. To model for co-regulation events, so-called forks, consisting of a peak linked to two TFs or a peak linked to two genes, are also being tested for conditional independence and filtered by significance. For the final GRN, regulatory motif triplets are only kept if they show internal consistency, meaning that the final sign of the multiplication of the three possible pairwise correlations is positive.

RENIN⁴³

RENIN approaches GRN inference from paired scATAC-seq and scRNA-seq by focusing on finding accurate CREs. The multiomics data is stored in a Seurat object and first aggregated as metacells through a modified version of VISION's⁴⁴ microclustering algorithm. By default, metacells are composed of 100 cells and 10 cells for scATAC and scRNA arrays, respectively. A multivariate regression model first associates potential CREs to genes located within 500 kb of the TSS, using the peak accessibility to model gene expression. The adaptive elastic-net model is used to handle the sparsity and the numerous collinear variables in single-cell data, with both a L1 penalty to reduce the rate of false positives regulations, and a L2 penalty to increase stability of the model in such high dimensional spaces. Once CREs have been associated with genes, TFs are linked to CREs and promoters through TF binding motif information from CIS-BP⁴. Motifs are added to the Seurat object for each peak by the AddMotifs function of Signac⁴⁵. TF are then associated to genes through these motifs and CREs-genes associations. Finally, a second adaptive elastic-net model is run to predict which TFs are likely to regulate a target gene. The inferred regulatory links are signed and can be ranked through their regulatory coefficients.

scAI⁴⁶

scAI aggregates and integrates paired scRNA-seq and scATAC-seq data using an iterative matrix factorization model. Before running the model, count matrices stored in an scAI object are subjected to quality control, normalized to account for library size, and highly variable features are selected. Factors are then derived as low-dimensional representations that correspond to known biological processes or signals related to a particular cell type. For each of these factors, factor-specific marker genes and peaks are identified based on a differential ranking approach. Next, candidate peak-gene relationships are assigned if a marker peak is located 250 kb up- or downstream of the TSS of a marker gene. From the candidate peak-gene relationships, regulatory links are identified using a perturbation approach. In this approach, the Pearson correlation between the expression level of the gene and the accessibility level of the peak is calculated and compared to a perturbed correlation where either the expression level or the accessibility are set to 0. From this, a differential correlation is calculated which is used to select relevant peak-gene interactions. For the identification of TF-gene links, scAI uses motifmatchr²¹ with TF motifs from CIS-BP⁴ to infer TF activities for each peak linked to a gene from the scATAC-seq data. A non-negative least squares regression model is then fit to the gene expression levels based on the obtained TF activities for each peak. Finally, TF-gene links are inferred if the regression coefficient of a TF is greater than zero.

sc-compReg⁴⁷

sc-compReg performs comparative GRN analysis between two conditions from log₂-transformed gene expression count matrices and log₂-transformed scATAC-seq matrices with consistent cluster assignments across unpaired modalities potentially obtained from coupled non-negative matrix factorization. First, it builds a scaffold GRN for each condition by assigning peaks to target genes that overlap in an undefined window from each gene's TSS and TFs to peaks using an undefined motif matcher with an undefined motif database following the PECA³⁸ workflow. sc-compReg then identifies differentially expressed genes between the two conditions using a *t*-test. For each TF-gene pair in the scaffold GRN where the gene is differentially expressed, it computes a regulatory potential score for both conditions independently based on the expression of the TF across cells, the TF binding motif strength across peaks, the accessibility level of the open peaks and the interaction strength between each peak-gene. Differential TF-gene edges between the conditions are then selected if the regulatory potential of a TF is different between both conditions and the association/correlation between TF and target gene differs. This is done by fitting a linear model that predicts the obtained regulatory potential scores from the expression level of the target gene across cells and the condition it belongs to. sc-compReg then compares the obtained coefficients to a null distribution based on a Gamma distribution to detect the final differential TF-gene links.

SCENIC+⁴⁸

SCENIC+ infers enhancer-based GRNs from paired scRNA-seq and scATAC-seq data. The input data is provided as raw transcript counts stored in an AnnData object alongside a cisTopic object containing candidate enhancers identified from topic modeling on preprocessed ATAC-seq data and a motif enrichment dictionary. Preprocessing for input object generation includes peak calling on cell type-specific pseudo-bulk profiles and merging into a consensus peak set. Only cells that pass the QC of both data modalities are kept. To identify candidate enhancers, a predefined number of co-accessible region sets are modeled using pycisTopic. Region-set probabilities are binarized and differential accessible regions are computed. The putative enhancers are then used as input for motif matching. To calculate TF-peak links the pre-computed cisTarget motif database and the pycisTarget⁴⁸ motif matching algorithm, which also includes a wrapper to HOMER⁶, are used. For each TF a union set of genomic regions that contain a corresponding binding motif is created. To infer the final eGRN, the nonlinear tree-based Gradient Boosting Machine regression approach is used to compute TF-gene links, based on co-expression, and peak-gene links, considering all consensus peaks within a defined search window of 1 - 150 kb around the TSS. Positively and negatively correlating links are separated by Pearson correlation. Finally, modules are created by intersecting the binarized TF-peak and peak-gene relationships by region name. The resulting modules are optimized by running GSEA⁴⁹ on all genes of a module using the importance scores from the TF-gene or peak-gene relationships as the ranking. Regulons are generated from all leading-edge genes and their linked binarized peaks while the ones containing less than 10 target genes or obtained from negatively correlated peak-gene connections are discarded. Further downstream GRN velocity can be used to assess branched and unbranched trajectories.

scMEGA⁵⁰

scMEGA infers GRNs along a user-defined trajectory from either paired scRNA-seq and scATAC-seq data. For the latter it leverages FigR's integration method. It requires two Seurat objects storing the gene expression and the chromatin accessibility data as well as a gene score matrix. Once the data is multimodal, it performs dimension reduction for user-selected clusters by diffusion map using destiny⁵¹. From the obtained embedding it computes pseudotime scores for a trajectory of interest using ArchR's³³ approach and ranks cells accordingly. Next, scMEGA associates TFs to peaks from the peak count matrix using the method MOODs¹⁹ and the motif database JASPAR¹⁰. It then computes TF activities at the single-cell level from the obtained TF-peaks interactions and the peak counts with chromVar²¹. To account for sparsity pseudotime points (TPs) are created from the ordered cells in the trajectory by smoothing their values using a windowed mean. Potential relevant TFs in the trajectory are selected by computing the Pearson correlation between TF activities and TF log-normalized gene expression across TPs, filtering for a correlation greater than 0.3 and a

false discovery rate smaller than 0.01. Similarly, potential relevant genes in the trajectory are selected by subsetting the top 90th percentile of most variable genes. Then, it calculates the Pearson correlation between the TP-scaled log-normalized gene expression and the TP-scaled log-normalized peaks. Finally, it filters the obtained peak-gene links by genomic distance to the gene's TSS (250 kb up- or downstream), positive correlation and significance. Afterwards, scMEGA infers TF-gene links by computing the Pearson correlation between the TP-scaled TF activities and the TP-scaled log-normalized gene expression for the relevant TFs and genes obtained before. Finally, TF-gene links are kept if a given TF has a matching motif in a peak that is associated with a given gene.

scMTNI⁵²

scMTNI is a probabilistic graphical method that uses multi-task learning to infer cell type specific GRNs from a cell lineage tree and unpaired scRNA-seq and ATAC-seq data. It first generates a scaffold GRN for each cell type from cluster-specific BAM files from the ATAC-seq data. For each cell type, the BAM files are pooled to create pseudo-bulk accessibility profiles, and TF motif scores are calculated based on the log-ratio of PWMs to a uniform background per peak, as defined in the PIQ toolkit⁵³ using the CIS-BP⁴ motif database. scMTNI then assigns motifs to each ATAC-seq peak and links the peak to a gene if the TSS is located within 5 kb up- or downstream of the peak, resulting in TF-peak-gene interactions. Since multiple peaks mapped to one TF can be assigned to the same gene, scMTNI selects the maximum motif score across all possible peaks as the TF-gene's interaction weight. Finally, the resulting binary scaffold GRN is generated by keeping the top 20% of the TF-gene interactions based on the motif scores. To build the final cell type specific GRNs, scMTNI leverages dependency networks, a class of probabilistic graphical methods, modeling the normalized gene expression of each cluster as a random variable that depends on a set of TFs. The model is composed of two priors, the cell type specific scaffold GRN obtained in the previous step, and the cell lineage structure as the probability of a TF-gene edge in a cell type presumably depends on its state in the predecessor cell type. With these, the model obtains cell type specific GRN weights by estimating the posterior distribution from each cell type's RNA-seq data.

SOMatic⁵⁴

SOMatic leverages self organizing maps (SOMs), an unsupervised deep learning embedding technique, to build GRNs from unpaired scRNA-seq and scATAC-seq data. As input SOMatic requires RNA-seq data after RSEM⁵⁵-quantification and mapped DNA sequencing and peak data as SAM and BED files, respectively. SOMatic begins by training a SOM for RNA-seq and ATAC-seq separately, and then identifies meta-clusters for each SOM. For each possible meta cluster pair between both omics, SOMatic maps peaks to target genes if they are located 25 kb up- or downstream of the gene's TSS. Next, it assigns TFs to each peak by performing motif analysis with FIMO²⁸ using the motif database HOCOMOCO¹⁵. To keep only specific TF-peak interactions, a one-tailed z -score test of the motif presence in a peak across paired metaclusters is computed and non-significant ones are removed. Finally, SOMatic links all significant TFs to their downstream target genes across pairs of meta clusters, obtaining the final GRN.

Symphony^{56,57}

Symphony is a probabilistic hierarchical multi-view mixture method that deconvolutes bulk ATAC-seq data into cell type profiles and integrates these with scRNA-seq data to infer cell type specific GRN in an unpaired manner. It uses accessibility matrices, quantified as the peak height, and log-transformed normalized gene count matrices as input. Symphony fits latent parameters simultaneously in an integrative model with three components. (1) The epigenetic component models cell type specific ATAC-seq profiles by assuming that bulk profiles are represented as a weighted sum depending on the proportion of clusters in a sample. (2) The GRN component assumes that regulatory links are dependent on genome accessibility by building cell type scaffold GRNs from the ATAC-seq data. First it maps TFs to peaks using FIMO²⁸ with an undefined motif database, and then it assigns each peak to the closest gene's TSS, generating TF-gene pairs. (3) The expression component assumes that log-transformed gene expression follows a multivariate normal

distribution. For each TF-gene pair, it defines a mode of regulation depending on the sign of their empirical covariance at the gene expression level. This weight is further refined by propagating covariances through the graph using a path length of two, capturing indirect regulation events, resulting in the final GRN per cell type.

TimeReg⁵⁸

TimeReg builds a GRN and identifies key regulators for each time point in a trajectory from paired ATAC-seq and RNA-seq data. It first builds a scaffold GRN for each time point from normalized expression and accessibility data provided as TXT files following a similar framework as PECA³⁸. It assigns peaks to target genes that overlap in an undefined window from each gene's TSS, and assigns TFs on the peaks using HOMER⁶ with motifs from an undefined database. Then, it defines a trans-regulation score for each TF-gene pair based on the TF's expression level, the enrichment of the TF's motif in the possible peaks and the co-expression between the TF and the gene. For each peak-gene pair, TimeReg also computes a cis-regulation score that is based on the TF motif binding score, the interaction strength from the peak-gene interaction, the peak normalized accessibility and the previously computed trans-regulation score. Finally, it identifies driver TFs that show different trans-regulation scores on up-regulated genes across the trajectory.

TRIPOD⁵⁹

TRIPOD infers GRNs from paired scRNA-seq and scATAC-seq data provided in a Seurat object. In the following, multiple data objects storing information about peak accessibility, motif scores, gene expression etc. are extracted to be submitted to TRIPOD. By default, open chromatin regions are scanned with chromVAR²¹ for motifs from the JASPAR¹⁰ database. To account for sparsity in the data the cells are first pooled into metacells by the weighted nearest neighbor method as implemented in Seurat. Next, peaks are associated with genes if they are located in a search window of 100 kb upstream and 100 kb downstream of the TSS. To build the GRN, TRIPOD infers regulatory trios using two different approaches. In the first nonparametric method metacells are matched in a pairwise manner while fixing either TF expression or peak accessibility and discarding matches below a user defined threshold. Here, regulatory trios are determined by first computing the Spearman correlation between the differences of the two variables and secondly applying a regression model that describes the differences in gene expression with the linear combination of the differences in peak accessibility and the product of the differences in peak accessible and mean TF expression in the matched pairs. Depending on the fixed parameter, the regression model can also describe the differences in TF expression and the product of the differences in TF expression and mean peak accessibility. In the second approach, the parametric approach, multiple linear regression models are used on the individual metacells to estimate the gene expression change per change in TF expression with fixed peak accessibility or per change in peak accessibility with fixed TF expression. For both approaches the final GRN is constructed by filtering regulatory trios by significance.

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